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GAMES AND GAMIFICATION IN BLENDED ENGINEERING EDUCATION

J.F.J. Pruyn

Delft University of Technology
Delft, The Netherlands
ORCID: 0000-0002-4496-4544

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ABSTRACT

Blended learning is a powerful way to make the student responsible for their learning. However, ensuring proper preparation is often difficult. Motivation can be gained by a stimulating application of knowledge. Games and gamification can provide both a strong incentive, support and application of knowledge for blended learning.

This paper will identify the relevant theory to support this idea as well as discuss a new application for the Maritime Engineering programme at the Delft University of Technology. The development is done in a bachelor level course and uses gamification in the form of a VR practice to teach relevant practical insights, this is a new development and the first insights will be shared.

1 INTRODUCTION

In 2002 it was predicted that blended learning would become the standard of higher education [1]. COVID-19 and the need to teach millions of students remotely was not yet an issue or even foreseen at that time. Of course, COVID-19 has given blended education a significant boost [2-6], breaking existing reluctance and demonstrating the possibilities of online, remote and especially blended learning. Much of the staff indicates that they will keep quite some aspects of online teaching alive, even when the universities reopen completely.

Osguthorpe and Graham [7] are mostly cited as the first publication using the term Blended-Learning, but the approach of course started much earlier, with various attempts to make use of a combination of online and regular education. In an extensive literature study by Güzer and Caner [8], blended learning is linked to distant learning, which goes back to the correspondence and discussion by letter between various scholars and also their (former) students. However, blended learning is much broader. It does contain a, to some extent self-paced, or asynchronous part of the remote study (supported by technology), but also contains a synchronous element where this knowledge is applied, discussed or otherwise deepened. It is also quite often linked to flipping-the-classroom, where students study individually first and use lectures to apply the theory, instead of hearing about the theory in class and practising on their own.

In this paper blended learning is combined with gamification and applied to two distinct course developments. The first course is a first-year bachelor course and this is a new development, whereas the other development started about 10 years ago and has led to a successful course design that is now not only provided at the home institute but also seven other education programmes. While the first one serves to inspire and convey lessons learned after one year of implementation, the long-term application of the second one allowed us to pinpoint critical aspects to consider in such an application and link this further to existing educational theories.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. In the next session games and gamification are shortly discussed from a literature perspective, to underline why such approaches were chosen, although not that common in Engineering Education. As it is not the goal of this paper to provide a complete overview, reference is made to recent overview papers on the relevant subjects. This is followed by the discussion of both developments and concluded with a short reflection.

2 LITERATURE STUDY

Games and gamification are often not clearly distinguished in daily conversations. They are, however, two quite different concepts when consulting the scientific literature. Albeit, that these two terms do show some overlap in coverage. There is even a third term, though not often linked to academic education, which is game-based learning. It is relevant in this discussion of terminology as it also could overlap parts of the previous two terms. This is represented in Figure 1 below, showing large distinct areas, but also overlap between two terms and even all three terms. Serious games

in general is a term used for any game (offline and online) used to introduce a concept to the players. It is often introduced to change cultures or discuss new perspectives in a relatively safe environment [9-12]. Game-based learning (GBL) is a game focussed on learning certain materials. E.g. an online typewriting course in the form of a game, or online mathematic games for children. The difference is that in the serious game, the game itself is the learning goal, whereas, in game-based learning, the learning goals are supported by creating an actual game around it [13-15].

Figure 1: Representation of the three main game concepts in education.

The third term is gamification, which means the use of game mechanics to enliven the coursework. It should be clear that GBL is a form of gamification, but it results in an actual game. However, with gamification, the goal is not to create a game, but only to apply game elements to a regular learning situation. A scoreboard for good behaviour in primary schools is an example, but also the election of an employee of the month, or earning credits and status with activities on your favourite forum. Also in this case there is a clear overlap between this term and the other two [16-19]. To conclude an example that should illustrate the differences; using a list of equations and asking a student to solve as many as possible in a set time, is a form of gamification. However executed online in a race simulation against other students would be game-based learning and finally being required to do many similar equations, though not explicitly, to take the right decision, could be part of a serious game, with a focus on education.

With these differences identified, recent research in this area is discussed next. The use of GBL in academic education is not discussed in the literature to our knowledge and the amount of literature on serious games is also quite limited. However, gamification is studied quite extensively and although not often in the same, or even a related field, a benefit is that it allows for different mechanics in a game to be researched independently. As in each application, a limited choice of mechanics is only applied and this can be varied.

Most game-related research investigates motivation [16-19] and concludes on the aspects that promote or hinder the motivation of the participants. There are many game aspects study for their impact on motivation. A common division is given below

with a brief explanation to give an idea of the elements relevant when considering gamification:

- Achievements; what is your current progress or an award after completing an element.
- Social; Interact with others, learn from each other, but also compete with others.
- immersion/onboarding; how much the experience draws you in, is it addictive to continue
- Freedom of choice/to fail and feedback; the fact that you are encouraged to learn from mistakes instead of repeating the teacher.
- Visible Status/Leaderboard; how are you doing compared to others? Strong links with achievements and social aspects.
- Personalization; to what extent can you create your experience. This is not only the creation of a character but also the option to skip certain parts or to try out your ideas.

Almost all game aspects influence the motivation of the students involved positively. Several researchers warn against the use of a leader board [16, 20] however. The reason for this is that although it does affect the average and well-performing students positively, it also seems to cause disengagement by the students in the bottom quarter to third. Therefore, this should be applied with care and preferably in such a way that it motivates all students and allows for the formulation of achievable goals.

Students have a limited capacity to absorb new information [21], which is also known as the cognitive load theory. When using a game in education, learning the game may already take a lot of the learning capacity of the student. Either significantly increasing the time required to complete the course or reducing the actual learning, as many aspects are not considered and therefore not understood. The burden of learning the software is often underestimated by expert users. This is not only the case with games, but relates to any new tool introduced as a means to reach the learning goal. The use of CFD software in hydromechanics classes would also require a lot of consideration on how to approach learning the tool and its limitations as well as the goals of the course. When not properly addressed, learning results will be below the expectations or the required effort will far exceed the intended course load.

Finally, the idea of using VR in education is not new, already in 1996, a paper was presented on how to use VR for teaching experiments with potential risks to students [22]. However, since 2015 a strong increase in publication on the subject is seen [23]. Although a search on applications in the maritime field yielded only one result [24] with a focus on safety training, the amount of literature on the subject is actually large. With a slightly wider search on engineering education, the result set was abundant and a choice was made to focus on recent review papers with a focus on benefits and problems and related to engineering education to pick out the key lessons. This was done as the majority either described an application of VR in education or summarized the state of the art based on these papers, without judging the applicability of VR for education.

In general, the majority of applications of VR are found in engineering education [23, 25], though the applications may vary from teaching about VR to teaching in VR. When considering teaching in VR, the goal in this project, visualization covers about two-thirds of the applications. Training and operations are only one-third. Potkonjak et al. [26] might have a good explanation for that. A key issue with VR is that it does not feel real and a student may be tempted to become playful, rather than serious. To counter this sessions should not be overly long and portrair a high sense of reality.

Based on the discussed literature games and simulators offer a way of applying knowledge and increase the intrinsic motivation of students to learn the course subjects. With these benefits in mind, as well as the warning on cognitive overloading and the disengagement potential of leader boards, two applications in the course programmes have been designed. The use of VR simulations to learn about shipbuilding at the start of their study and the use of a serious game to learn about the link between economics and technology towards the end of their studies. These implementations will be discussed next.

3 RESULTS

To apply the idea of gaming/gamification to a course is of course not new. Even within the curriculum of Maritime Technology, there is already a longstanding use of a serious business game for teaching economics and law to the master students. This course is not only offered at TU Delft but also other master programmes related to maritime technology and maritime economics. It is the success of this course that led to the initiation of the use of VR in the bachelor course.

Within this chapter, the development of the VR exercises for the first-year bachelor course is discussed. Each section will discuss one step of the ADDIE approach for course development [27], Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation and Evaluation. The main focus is on the design as this was the first year of implementation and only partially executed due to an increase in the Covid-19 measures during the course.

3.1 Bachelor Course Analysis

Several lecturers of the second- and third-year bachelor had the feeling that the basic knowledge and vocabulary had declined compared to five years ago. Although there was no concrete evidence at this stage, it was indicated that more often than before they had to explain concepts that were previously known by the students.

Based on a discussion between various staff members, it was hypothesized that the source of this was a combination of adaptations to the curriculum. First, the industry practice in the first year was cancelled, due to capacity issues. This meant that a strong frame of reference (working 2-3 weeks in steel construction) was lost. Furthermore, the set-up of a small course and a small project was replaced by one large project. This meant that students had to learn the vocabulary within the project. However, as for the project mentor groups of 6-8 students were used, work was often divided between the students. In turn, this led to not studying all materials, but only a fraction.

Unfortunately, there was not yet enough data available to verify this assumption, something to be addressed in the redevelopment as well.

3.2 Bachelor Course Design

It was decided to redevelop the course set-up, using blended learning to allow for a more individual learning approach. In Figure 3 the content focus of the course is displayed. Each subject represents a week of study, the remaining three weeks of the course are used for a project assignment, where all knowledge is combined and brought together. To ensure that the students study the materials the week before, the knowledge is provided in the form of lecture notes, book chapters, videos, and papers. The first evaluation is a formative quiz to assess the knowledge. Students are given 10 random questions and need to answer 8 correctly. They do have as many re-sits as they require. As information literacy is part of the course, they are also searching and studying papers on the subject and finally, the lecture time is used to further work with the subjects. This could be a pub quiz, or a small assignment to work out in the classroom or in one case even a take-home assignment.

Figure 2: Blended set-up as an alternative for an internship.

Figure 3: Course subjects

To support the development of a frame of reference a combination of practical exercises was designed to cover the most important aspects and insights from the actual industry practice. As can be seen in Figure 2. There is practical work in a workshop, there are virtual exercises related to production in a VR environment and there is video material (in 360-degrees) to show all elements. Finally, there is a yard simulation to study the relations between activities in a playful way.

As can be seen in Figure 2, there are four VR-Exercises. The complete set takes about two hours to complete for a group of four students. VR was chosen from an immersive perspective. With the goggles and headset on, you are completely cut off of the actual world and fully immersed in the virtual world. As we also added shipyard sounds, the

only thing missing is the smell of welding and grinding steel. For each element, the goal is clearly described, but students are left completely free in the way they pursue this and are learning from their mistakes and experiences, rather than from lecturers explaining it. Furthermore, each exercise has its unique focus and aspects and will be shortly described below.

The first exercise is called searching. This is an individual exercise where students are asked to find 10 randomly selected ship elements within the VR ship. (See also Figure 4). This tests the vocabulary learned in the first two weeks of the course and makes the student familiar with the VR environment and controls. To allow for the cognitive load, this exercise is performed individually, reducing the complexity of the exercise. The gamification aspects that are introduced within this part, are a leader board for the fastest time and the instant reward for correctly identifying an object in the form of your next task (visually in your VR world). There is no overall competition, just between the four students in the session.

Figure 4: Search (top right) and Transportation (Left and bottom right) exercise impressions.

In the second exercise, the students are transporting a pipe piece through the ship. The key goal here is to understand how cumbersome this can be for the people working on the yard and again to understand how much time is lost on transportation. In this case, time is not measured, but the students are given a real piece of pipe in their hands, which is also visible in the VR world. This enhances the immersion significantly [26] and is to our knowledge the only example of such an application. The weight of about 25 kg is a good motivator to try to complete the session as soon as possible, with a clear reward in the form of letting go. As with the previous exercise this one is also done in pairs, though without walkie-talkies, hence similar socialization is achieved as well.

The third exercise is called installation. In this part, two students work together to correctly install a number of stiffeners on a plate. This requires the use of a crane as well as communication via (virtual) walkie-talkies. The key goal of this exercise is to experience that even relatively simple actions in shipbuilding tend to take quite a long time. Especially when communication is hampered by one-way traffic (with walkie-talkies, you cannot hear the other one if you are pressing the talk button, so waiting and clear closing statements are key). As the sense of time is not easy in the VR world the time is measured and discussed with the students afterwards. The progress to the end goal, installing three stiffeners, is easy to follow visually and the socialisation is also present as there is one crane operator and one metalworker who have to work together.

Figure 5: Installation (top) and Communication (bottom) exercise impressions.

The last exercise is done with all four students. It is focused on moving a section (a large part of the ship construction) into place. Clear communication is a key element here, as the crane driver cannot see and avoid all obstacles just by himself. With four people the issues in clear communication are increased. Also, the fact that this process is very slow, due to the danger of swinging and damaging the construction, is conveyed in this exercise. Although not addressed with the previous two exercises, the cognitive load is supported by slowly increasing the difficulty of the exercises and allowing for familiarisation with the controls and concepts in the previous exercises.

3.3 Bachelor Course Development and Implementation

The VR practicals were developed with the support of the VRZone, an organisation within the TUDelft with the goal to support both the access of students to VR and the implementation of VR in education. The total duration of the exercises is about two hours, keeping in line with the recommendations of not doing long exercises [26]. The results were already shown in Figures 4 and 5. Unfortunately, due to the COVID-19 situation, only about half the students were able to do the VR exercises in the first year, as the library was locked down for the second half of the course and even the next quarter.

3.4 Bachelor Course Evaluation

Based on [27] evaluation consists of three distinct aspects: perception, learning and performance. As this was the first year of implementation, results on this aspect are incomplete and mostly informal or subjective. In the next years, more data will be collected to identify the impact of the changes and to continuously improve knowledge attainment and retention.

The perception evaluation in this course consists of two parts. An informal discussion at the end of the session between the students and TAs; What was good, what could be improved. The feedback received was positive, students appreciated the insights and possibility to do something and check their knowledge in this way. The second part is the faculty course evaluation form, usually provided three weeks after the quarter ends. In the last year only seven out of 63 students filled in this evaluation. Furthermore, as another element of the course did not go smoothly, this received the most attention in the review and it is not possible to draw any conclusions for the VR part at this moment.

The learning achieved is assessed by the lecturer and consists of the exam results. Compared to previous years a slightly larger fraction has completed the course, though based on this single observation, this could be regular variation, an influence of the lockdown or an actual improvement in knowledge absorption. Overall there was consensus between the lecturers that in the final group assignment, fewer questions on processes vocabulary were asked, especially considering that an excursion to a real shipyard, was not possible this year, but did take place in the previous years.

The final element is performance. As the initial complaint that started this course revision was a lack of knowledge retention, especially on the side of vocabulary and process knowledge, the focus of this part should be on establishing the knowledge retained from this course. In order to assess if an increase in knowledge retention is

achieved, the quiz questions used in the self-study part of the course are re-used at the start of follow-up second and third-year courses. As this was the first application of the course, we cannot study the results yet but it has given us some insight into the retention rate. Irrespective of the year of the later course, the students of the previous course set-up scored on average around 35-40% correct in their answers. This is a low score, especially when considering the question focus on basic concepts and principles. What this value does indicate, is that there is merit in the initial observation that the knowledge level is quite low and perhaps even lower than before. If the redevelopment of the course is a success, an increase in the test scores would be expected. The results will be monitored for the coming years, with these values forming the baseline values to compare against.

4 REFLECTIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

Comparing the development of the VR application with the development of the business game, this is only the beginning. It took at least five years to fine-tune all aspects of the latter course and the VR application was only applied one time so far. Understanding both the capacity limitations as well as how gamification can impact the motivation and results, has helped the creation of these exercises and provided solid ground to continue these developments.

The formative assessments at the start of the follow-up course we're also a new development. These also will require some further fine-tuning but would be a valuable addition to the bachelor in general. Supporting both the lecturer of the preceding and following course in assessing the knowledge retained or present at the start. Furthermore, it would provide students with this insight as well and could be accompanied by links to previous work to facilitate a quick recapture of previous work.

To conclude, the implementation of gamification in courses could support an increase in knowledge retention as the students learn from experience, rather than from instructions. The results for the current case course development are not yet sufficient to validate this at this point, but the impact will be monitored and evaluated in the coming years, leading to a follow-up of this work with a focus on the impact measured.

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